

Inequality Report 2021:
India's Unequal Healthcare Story, Oxfam India

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Abstract

On July 20, 2021, Oxfam India released a valuable and timely document focusing on the current COVID-19 health emergency and its implications on socio-economic order: especially in terms of inequalities due to absence of universal access to health care services. This has left the essential services to the vagaries of the ruthless market forces. In five chapters, the report details the profile of health inequities, impact of health interventions and inequalities of outcomes in India, efficacy of government interventions and intersectional marginalities of caste, class ethnicity, gender, religion and location exacerbating existing inequalities and reveals how the neoliberal economic policies are enabling a super-rich elite and necro-capitalists to amass wealth in the middle of the worst deflationary spiral and the worst economic crisis in the post-independence period, while crores of dispossessed masses are struggling to survive, and millions are left hungry, malnourished and homeless.

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Increase in Intersectional Marginalities and Inequity in Health Outcomes

The report reveals startling data and states that 2/3 households belonging to the general category have access to improved, non-shared sanitation facilities, while only 1/4th Scheduled Tribes (ST) households have improved, non-shared sanitation facilities. Majority of Scheduled Caste (SC) population have to live in the unhygienic conditions in the rural and urban areas and 12.6% more children among the SC households are stunted than the children in the general category.

For the bottom 1/5th population, chances for child mortality in 0-5 age group is 3 times higher as compared to the top 1/5th Indian population. Under the pandemic, in terms of health outcomes of general category are better than SCs and STs, rich are better than poor, Hindus are better than Muslims, urban is better than rural, men are better than women. It also reveals exacerbation on already existing stark inequalities after the imposition of nationwide lockdown in the first wave and partial and localized lockdowns during the second wave as a result of unemployment, hunger, homelessness, distress reverse migration and circular migration of millions of the working poor. The rich were economically secure and lived in the safety of gated communities, worked from home and could socially isolate themselves. They were also supported by the supplies of goods and services of the informal sector workforce and thereby able to escape the pandemic's worst impact.

Benefits for the Billionaires

The report highlights the how pandemic profiteers exponentially multiplied their incomes. The wealth of the Indian billionaires grew by 35% during the lockdown. For example, earnings of Ambani Group of Industries during the pandemic rose to

equivalent of earnings of the 40 crore informal workers who are currently leading lives of extreme deprivation and have their standard of living fallen below poverty line since July 2020. The report calculates that the increased wealth of the top 11 Indian billionaires' during the pandemic could have financed the National Rural Employment Guarantee Scheme (NREGS) or the public health budget for the next decade.

Precarity of the Informal Workers

The report brings to the fore a deplorable profile of the unorganized sector workers who have been the worst hit during last 15 months of the pandemic and avers that out of a total 122 million men and women who lost their jobs, 75% i.e. 92 million men and women workers/employees were rendered jobless in the informal sector. Exhaustion of savings within one month of lockdown, i.e. by May 2020, they were forced to vacate their rented dwellings due to their inability to pay the rents and this led to reverse migration of millions of men, women, children and elderly was full of multiple hardships, including starvation, dehydration, suicides, exhaustion, road and rail accidents, police brutality, denial of timely medical care and deaths. As per the official data, over 2582 cases of human rights violation were reported with the National Human Rights Commission (NHRC) within one month of nationwide lockdown during March-April 2020.

Digital Divide and Poor Children Forced out of Education

The report profiles distressing scenario of students from underserved communities driven out of school and college education due to inability to access online education as less than 15% rural households had an internet connection and only 4% of rural households had a computer. The girls from the poverty

groups and lower middle classes have been major casualties of school and college education as barely 16% of rural girls and women could either use a computer or the internet- the reason being no access to devices, or in case they had a computer or a smart phone, they could not afford regular recharges of data and also persisting lack of electricity supplies.

In the absence of the state stepping in to provide online accessibility and last mile connectivity to these out of school children and young adults, all the gains of last 150 years of modern education have been reversed and rampant incidences of child labour, forced marriages and child marriages and trafficking of children have occurred under the cloak of lockdown and the collapse of governance structures. Unregulated market of private providers of digital platforms are thriving and generating huge profits.

Socio-economic Determinants of Inequalities in Health and Sanitation Services

Oxfam India conducted a survey on health inequalities during the pandemic in seven states of Andhra Pradesh, Maharashtra, Uttar Pradesh, Delhi, Kerala, Bihar and Odisha. The survey revealed that 768 respondents were either infected with coronavirus or had recovered from COVID-19 onslaught. It showed that the percentage of respondents in higher income groups who could arrange for transport themselves was double than that of the low-income groups. Even the percentage of respondents who faced social stigma due to being COVID-19 positive was five times higher in low-income brackets than among COVID positive patients in high income brackets.

When it came to non-COVID-19 health services, only 18.2% in the general category faced hurdles while more than 50% of SCs and STs faced difficulties in accessing non-COVID medical facilities for patients with comorbidities and reproductive

health needs. We are aware that sanitation is the most important factor in containing coronavirus infection. Here too, there were inequalities in accessing clean and safe water and SC communities faced 4 times more hardships and were forced to manage with unsafe water sources. Even after 6 years of an official launch of 'Clean India Campaign', only 6% of the poorest 20% in the bottom of the economic pyramid have access to non-shared sources of sanitary toilets with running water, compared to 93.4% of the top 20% of the population. Physical distancing or body distancing as demanded by COVID-19 advisory was not possible for 60% of India's population which lives in one room tenements or are homeless.

Gender Differential Impact

The report brings out a startling figure the gender implications of the pandemic and state that within one month of the lockdown, 17 million women lost their jobs. In April 2020, more poorer women lost their livelihoods than their upper income counterparts. Moreover, the total time spent in both paid and unpaid activities by women rose, with increased labour intensity. Women have been working longer hours for paid work and simultaneously managing the daily chores of cooking, cleaning, procuring essentials, catering to the educational needs of the children and care work for all members of the family in the midst of varied health emergencies. The work-from-home culture has also blurred the lines between working hours and me-time. The survey results highlighted that gender-based violence has emerged as a major shadow pandemic and 33.9% women and 18.2% men respondents experienced anxiety, irritation and anger, and sleep deprivation during the lockdown.

Need for Fiscal Expansion

The report acknowledges that under Ayushman Bharat- Pradhan Mantri Jan Arogya Yojana (PMJAY) the scheme covered population living below poverty line, but it left out the uninsured poor and the middle class who were economically ruined by the rent-seeking private health providers. In this regard, the report applauds Kerala for robust public healthcare system as well as the farsighted response of the state government for allocating funds, functions and functionaries to combat COVID-19 pandemic.

The report urges that the budgetary allocation for public health must be enhanced to 2.5% of GDP so that preventive and promotive healthcare can be strengthened and out-of-pocket expenditure can be reduced. Public funding for education also demands budgetary allocation of 6% of GDP. Social security and social protection of informal sector workers in terms of registration of all workers and income support to the unemployed persons also demands financial allocation by the state. The report conveys that to finance the increased government expenditure is possible by progressive taxation of the richest members of the society as well as the corporate houses.

Conclusion

In essence, the Inequality Report 2021: India's Unequal Healthcare Story by Oxfam India is in the public domain and easily accessible on the internet is a must read for all. The findings of the report are an eye-opener and need urgent action towards resolution of the multiple challenges plaguing the country, especially by its poorer and vulnerable citizens. It definitely serves as a conscience keeper for all conscious citizens, sensitive policymakers and responsible administration as it provides insights from the grounded reality of life worlds of all sections of population and provides evidence-based policy recommendations.